

Condensation of Phenols with Ethyl N-Aryl-Formimidates

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Ethyl N-phenylformimide, ethyl N-5-chloro-2-methylphenylformimide, and ethyl N-2-chloro-4-methylphenylformimide are allowed to react with phenol, cresols, chlorophenols, dihydroxybenzenes, naphthols, anisol, and 2,6-dimethylphenol. In most cases, condensation takes place to yield the corresponding *o*-hydroxyanils as coloured crystals.

In 1947, Knott¹ reported his unsuccessful attempts to condense ethyl N-phenylformimide with phenol, *p*-cresol, dihydroxybenzenes, anisole, and 2,6-dimethylphenol. However, when our modified experimental conditions were applied, resorcinol gave the corresponding dianil, while phenol, *p*-cresol, anisole, catechol, hydroquinone, and 2,6-dimethylphenol failed to condense.

TABLE I

Condensation of Ethyl N-phenyl formimide with resorcinol and of Ethyl N-2-chloro-4-methylphenylformimide with Cresols

Name of Anil	m.p.(°C)	Yield (%)	Color with FeCl ₃	Formula	C	H	N	Cl
(a) resorcin-2,4-dialdehyde-dianil	202-203		red violet	known compound				
b) 2'-hydroxy-3'-methylbenzaldehyde-2-chloro-4-methyl anil	88-89	64.2	yellowish green	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ NOCl	Req. 69.29 F. 69.21	5.39 5.57	5.39 5.51	13.68 13.55
(c) 2'-hydroxy-4'-methylbenzaldehyde-2-chloro-4-methyl anil	111-112	64.5	red violet	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NOCl	Req. 69.29 F. 69.26	5.39 5.52	5.39 5.31	13.68 13.73
(d) 2'-hydroxy-5'-methylbenzaldehyde-2-chloro-4-methyl anil	132-133	68.0	red violet	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ NOCl	Req. 69.29 F. 69.22	5.39 5.50	5.39 5.53	13.68 13.51

Remarks :

(a) identified by its m.p. 202-203° (m.p. reported³ 202-203°) and hydrolysis to resorcin-2,4-dialdehyde, m.p. 127° (m.p. reported⁴ 127°); dioxime, m.p. 208° (m.p. reported^{4,5} 209°).

(b) hydrolyzed to 2-chloro-4-methylaniline, b.p. 83°/2 mm (b.p. reported⁶ 219°/732 mm); its acetyl derivative, m.p. 118° (m.p. reported⁶ 118°), and to 2-hydroxy-3-methylbenzaldehyde, b.p. 207-208° (b.p. reported⁷ 208-209°); semicarbazone, m.p. 247° (m.p. reported⁷ 248°).

(c) hydrolyzed to 2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzaldehyde, m.p. 55-56° (m.p. reported⁸ 56°); oxime, m.p. 106-107° (m.p. reported⁸ 108-109°).

(d) hydrolyzed to 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde, m.p. 55° (m.p. reported⁸ 56°); oxime, m.p. 105° (m.p. reported⁸ 105°).

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Since this imidate failed to react, higher boiling point imidates were tried. Thus, ethyl *N*-2-chloro-4-methylphenylformimidate was condensed with *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-cresols under modified conditions, and the corresponding anils were isolated (Table I). Similarly, ethyl *N*-5-chloro-2-methylphenylformimidate was condensed with phenol, chlorophenols, naphthols, and 2,6-dimethylphenol under our modified conditions. Except with phenol itself, and 2,6-dimethylphenol, the corresponding hydroxy anils were isolated (Table II).

TABLE II

Condensation of Ethyl N-5-Chloro-2-Methylphenylformimidate with Phenols

Name of Anil	m.p.(°C)	Yield (%)	Color with FeCl ₃	Formula	C	H	N	Cl
(e) 2'-hydroxy-3'-methylbenzaldehyde-5-chloro-2-methylanil	109-111	70.0	deep green	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ NOCl	Req. 69.29 F. 69.23	5.39 5.52	5.39 5.52	13.68 13.35
(f) 2'-hydroxy-4'-methylbenzaldehyde-5-chloro-2-methylanil	96-97	60.0	red violet	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ NOCl	Req. 69.29 F. 69.53	5.39 5.75	5.39 5.37	13.68 13.62
(g) 2'-hydroxy-5'-methylbenzaldehyde-5-chloro-2-methylanil	129-130	65.4	deep violet	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ NOCl	Req. 69.29 F. 69.21	5.39 5.50	5.39 5.58	13.68 13.35
(h) 2'-hydroxy-3'-chlorobenzaldehyde-5-chloro-2-methylanil	120-122	82.0	red violet	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NOCl	Req. 60.00 F. 60.13	3.93 3.84	5.00 4.87	25.36 25.20
(i) 2'-hydroxy-4'-chlorobenzaldehyde-5-chloro-2-methylanil	92-93	76.6	red violet	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NOCl ₂	Req. 60.00 F. 60.28	3.93 4.00	5.00 4.57	25.36 25.29
(j) 2'-hydroxy-5'-chlorobenzaldehyde-5-chloro-2-methylanil	88-89	82.0	red violet	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NOCl ₂	Req. 60.00 F. 60.10	3.93 3.72	5.00 4.90	25.36 25.30
(k) 1'-hydroxy-2'-naphthaldehyde-5-chloro-2-methylanil	155-156	78.0	yellowish green	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NOCl	Req. 73.10 F. 73.12	4.74 4.71	4.74 4.60	12.01 11.98
(l) 2'-hydroxy-1'-naphthaldehyde-5-chloro-2-methylanil	147-148	74.6	green	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NOCl	Req. 73.10 F. 73.00	4.74 4.77	4.74 4.59	12.01 11.91

(e) hydrolyzed to 2-hydroxy-3-methylbenzaldehyde which was identified as under (b).

(f) hydrolyzed to 2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzaldehyde which was identified as under (c).

(g) hydrolyzed to 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde which was identified as under (d).

(h) hydrolyzed to 3-chloro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde which was identified by its m.p. 53-54.5 (m.p. reported⁹ 54.5-55.5°); semicarbazone, m.p. 240-242° (m.p. reported⁹ 240-242°).

(i) hydrolyzed to 4-chloro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, m.p. 51-52° (m.p. reported⁹ 52.5°); benzoate derivative, m.p. 98° (m.p. reported¹⁰ 98.5°); semicarbazone, m.p. 209° (m.p. reported¹⁰ 212°).

(j) hydrolyzed to 5-chloro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, m.p. 98° (m.p. reported¹¹ 99.5°); oxime, m.p. 127-128° (m.p. reported¹¹ 128°).

(k) hydrolyzed to 1-hydroxy-2-naphthaldehyde, m.p. 57° (m.p. reported¹² 59-60°); oxime, m.p. 144-145° (m.p. reported¹² 145°).

(l) hydrolyzed to 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, m.p. 80° (m.p. reported¹³ 82°); oxime, m.p. 155° (m.p. reported¹³ 157°).

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The structures of each of the products were confirmed by (a) elemental analysis, (b) hydrolysis to the original amine and phenolic aldehyde, and (c) i.r. spectra which showed the presence of OH (2.8–2.9 μ) and $\bar{C} = N$ (6.15–6.2 μ) groups.

In all cases where reaction takes place, condensation occurs *exclusively* at the *ortho* position with respect to the phenolic OH group.

A plausible mechanism is suggested as follows :

The condensation seems to take place by an attack of the carbon atom of the $C = N$ group as an electrophilic center on the *o*-position of the phenol as a nucleophilic center. The reaction is assisted by the hydrogen bond formed between the nitrogen atom of the imidate and the hydrogen atom of the phenolic OH group, thus allowing the formation of a transition state of 6-membered ring. The final product is also able to form intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl N-arylformimidates were prepared according to the usual method². Ethyl N-2-chloro-4-methylphenylformimidate, b.p. 107–109/2 mm., and ethyl N-5-chloro-2-methylphenylformimidate, b.p. 109–111/1.8 mm.

o-Hydroxyanils : A mixture of ethyl N-arylformimidate (0.18 mole) and the purified phenol (0.4 mole) was placed on a 200-ml.r.b. flask fitted with a capillary tube and a condenser set for distillation. The flask was heated in an oil bath at a temperature around the boiling point of the phenol. The solutions darkened in colour as the reaction proceeded. Ethanol was removed from the reaction flask as soon as it was formed. The flask was then allowed to cool to about 100°, and excess phenol removed under reduced pressure. The crude product left in the reaction flask was dissolved in the minimum amount of acetone, and few mls. of distilled water was added with vigorous stirring until the oil separated set into a semi-solid mass. The solvent was decanted and the product was crystallised from absolute ethanol as coloured crystals.

Hydrolysis of the o-Hydroxyanils : A mixture of *o*-hydroxyanil (0.04 mole) and NaOH solution (10%, 100 ml) was refluxed for 2 hrs, allowed to cool to room temperature, and extracted twice with 30 ml portion ether. The combined ether extracts were dried over

anhydrous K_2CO_3 overnight. The solution was filtered, the solvent evaporated, and the remaining liquid was fractionated under reduced pressure. The distillate was identified as the original aromatic amine.

The alkaline solution was acidified with dil.HCl, and extracted twice with 30 ml portion ether. The ether extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 for 2 hrs. The solution was filtered, the solvent evaporated and the remaining product was identified as the *o*-hydroxy aromatic aldehyde.

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Received February 26, 1970